

EXCENTRIC

EXCENTRIC methodology

Milestone 5 Report – Transversal analysis methodology and plan

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Executive Summary

EXCENTRIC is a Horizon Europe Innovation Action project that develops and tests Collaborative Data Practices (CDP) across six pilot organizations in the Cultural and Creative Sectors and Industries (CCSI). Through real-life pilot environments, the project explores how Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs) can support a human-centric digital transition and contribute to strengthened sustainability and competitiveness. A shared conceptual and methodological spine is provided by the ARCHS Initial Framework¹ (Adaptive, Responsible, Collaborative, Human-Centric, Sustainable), which guides the project's diagnostics (WP2), acceleration (WP3), tool development and embedding (WP4), and transversal analysis (WP5).

This methodology establishes a shared approach to generating, analysing and integrating evidence within WP5 of the EXCENTRIC project. It specifies how insights from pilots, organisational practices, and tool development are systematically collected, analysed, and synthesised to ensure consistency while remaining sensitive to sectoral contexts. The methodology supports reflective learning within the project and ensures that empirical findings inform the accelerator process, tool development, and transferable recommendations. Specifically, this document aims to:

1. define a systematic transversal analysis methodology for EXCENTRIC, covering network analysis and cross-pilot synthesis across ARCHS dimensions, accelerator stages and piloting activities;
2. describe how this methodology ensures integration and cohesions across work packages, links data streams generated across different activities, and operationalize feedback loops into tool development and testing,
3. outline a practical plan for data collection analysis and reporting over the life of the project, aligned with milestones and key events, including the initial network analysis and cross-cutting theme assessment (M24).

This document provides shared methodological references for how the implementation evidence, generated across the EXCENTRIC pilots' activities integrates with the data collected for the purposes of the Network and Transversal Analysis (WP5) of the EXCENTRIC project. It is written primarily for the EXCENTRIC partners as a shared reference for data collection and analysis, an outline of the transversal analysis methodology, and a corresponding plan. It operationalizes WP1's objective of providing an integrated innovation and analysis framework and offers the measurement and analysis backbone for WP5, while enabling the structured data (and activities) feedback looping of the project structure.

This document constitutes the Milestone 5 Report (WP1, Task T1.2) and establishes the transversal analysis methodology and plan that will be implemented under WP5 (M13-M36). It guides WP5 implementation, with the first major synthesis checkpoint at Milestone 13 (M24: initial network analysis and cross-cutting theme assessment) and final consolidation feeding into D5.1 (M36).

¹ Derda et al. (2025). ARCHS Initial Framework.

1. Positioning WP5 in the EXCENTRIC Project Architecture

EXCENTRIC is structured as an iterative intervention that combines conceptual framing, pilot-based experimentation, technical development, and industry-level translation. Within this structure, WP5 functions as a transversal analytical and sensemaking layer that cuts across the project lifecycle.

Figure 1. Place of WP5 in the EXCENTRIC Project Architecture

WP5 is positioned across the project's core activities, connecting the conceptual understanding of Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs as a form of digital transition) with their practical application of the developed tools and practices in response to pilot challenges. It does so by analysing how CDE-related practices, tools, networks, and governance arrangements emerge and evolve across individual, organisational, and collaborative contexts, and how these processes are shaped through diagnostics, accelerator activities, and technical implementation (Figure 1). Therefore, WP5 links what is being designed and implemented in the pilots with how digital transition is experienced, negotiated, and stabilised in practice.

The ARCHS framework serves as an analytical spine through which this integration is achieved. Within WP5, ARCHS functions as both - a shared interpretive lens, a structuring device for transversal comparison, and a reference framework for reflecting on practice-level tensions and trade-offs. It enables WP5 to examine whether change occurs, under which conditions, through which configurations of practices, and with what implications for sustainability and competitiveness in the CCSI. Through this positioning, WP5 enables structured feedback loops across the project. Insights from transversal and network analysis are fed back into accelerator mentoring, tool refinement, and governance discussions, while

supporting the consolidation and translation of CDE practices beyond individual pilots.

The transversal analysis in EXCENTRIC is guided by the ambition to understand how Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs), when implemented under real-world conditions in the CCSI, relate to organizational sustainability and competitiveness. It is guided by the following question:

Which configurations of conditions (ARCHS-informed practices, tool embedding, accelerator exposure, and network properties) are associated with more sustainable and competitive outcome trajectories, and which elements can be scaled-up as transferable guidance for Collaborative Data Practice into experience sectors of CCSI?

Sub-questions are:

- How do ARCHS-informed practices and governance choices shape the way Collaborative Data Ecosystems are enacted across different pilot contexts?
- How do human, organisational, legal, and technological (f)actors interact and negotiate their roles within emerging Collaborative Data Ecosystems, and how do these interactions condition pathways of change?
- Which characteristics and configurations of Collaborative Data Ecosystem (co)relate with strengthened sustainability and competitiveness in the CCSI?

2. EXCENTRIC Transversal Analysis Hybrid Methodology

2.1 Methodological outlook

The EXCENTRIC transversal analysis adopts a **hybrid, theory-based and case-comparative approach**, combining:

(a) **Theory of Change** to structure the expected chain from activities/outputs to mechanisms and outcome both at pilot and project level:

(b) **Social Network Analysis informed by Actor-Network Theory** to describe and interpret evolving actor configurations and points of tension (human and non-human) in CDE assessment; and

(c) **(Q)QCA-inspired cross-pilot “matrix of change”** to compare pilots as configurations of conditions and outcomes, supporting structured learning under causal complexity rather than counterfactual attribution.

The Theory of Change framework is employed to map the intended impact of interventions, identify the causal relationships between activities and outcomes, and clarify the assumptions governing expected results. Network Analysis (drawing on Social Network Analysis and Actor-Network Theory) maps relational and socio-technical interactions among stakeholders, including both human and non-human actors. This enables the identification of key actors, roles, and influence patterns, as well as the processes, negotiations, and points of tension involved in the development of Collaborative Data Ecosystems. Taken together, this approach enables both an in-depth understanding of change pathways and a comparative examination of how different configurations of practices, relationships and conditions shape Collaborative Data Ecosystems and Practices across pilots.

Theory of Change	Social Network Analysis & Actor Network Theory
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Offers a structured logic model, identifying inputs, outputs, outcomes, and long-term impacts within and explicit change logic. (ii) Allows for the articulation of pathways of change and the assumptions underlying expected changes. (iii) It is used for mapping objectives against interventions and observable outcome dimensions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Examines how relationships among human and non-human actors are formed, negotiated, and stabilised in the process of developing collaborative data practices. (ii) Supports the identification of roles, alignments, frictions, and translations that shape how actors participate in, resist, or reshape collaborative data ecosystems. (iii) Enables the interpretation of social, institutional, and socio-technical dynamics that condition how collaborative data practices evolve over time.
(Quanti)Quali Comparative Analysis²	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Provides the cross-pilot logic for examining how different combinations of conditions are associated with different outcome trajectories across the six pilots, (ii) Supports structured small-N comparison by treating each pilot as a case defined by a configuration of conditions and outcomes, rather than estimating average effect or linear drivers, (iii) Is conducted as interpretive synthesis, guided through the ARCHS Framework and is anchored in the within-case change narratives. 	

Table 1. Methodological pillars description

In other words, while ToC supports the sequential input-output logical chain of the pilots path towards change, SNA and ANT show the how and why with regards to Collaborative Data Ecosystems, (Q)QCA describes and compares trajectories of change across pilots in light of commonalities or differences in conditions (human practices, organisational and operational specificities, network configurations, tool integration, and contextual constraints).^{3,4} For each pilot, quantitative data are combined with qualitative material, implementation traces, and network analysis outputs to construct a **pilot change narrative**: a concise synthesis describing (i) how sustainability and competitiveness evolved, (ii) which ARCHS-related capability and practice shifts were observed, (iii) how network conditions and tool embedding supported or hindered change, and (iv) which elements of the CDE stabilised, scaled, or remained fragile. Table 2 provides an overall look on the different layers of analysis on the EXCENTRIC change narrative. These within-case narratives form the empirical and interpretive foundation for subsequent cross-pilot comparison.

Detailed instruments, lines of inquiry, and supporting data structures are provided in the

² Befani (2020). Choosing Appropriate Evaluation Methods; Ragin (2008). Redesigning social inquiry: Fuzzy sets and beyond.

³ Given the complexity of the intervention and the absence of experimental counterfactuals, WP5 assesses plausible contribution rather than strict causality and uses configurational reasoning to make “which combinations mattered” explicit and transparent.

⁴ Befani, B. & O'Donnell, M. (2016) Choosing Appropriate Evaluation Methods: A Tool for Assessment and Selection. Mayne, J. (2011). Contribution analysis: Addressing cause and effect.

Annexes to ensure transparency and replicability.

An overview of ARCHS-aligned measurement instruments and inquiry frameworks is provided in **Annex 1** (ARCHS Measurement and Inquiry Framework).

	Built from	What it shows
Sustainability & Competitiveness baseline and deltas (per pilot)	Indicator processing (normalisation where appropriate; aggregation into outcome domains; T0–T2 comparison; T1 if feasible).	How each pilot’s sustainability and competitiveness profile changes over time by domain/identified indicators, without reducing results to a single composite index.
Pilot change narrative (one per pilot)	S&C deltas plus selected ARCHS-coded qualitative data plus key network descriptors (micro/meso/macro).	A concise explanation of how and why the observed deltas plausibly occurred, and what stabilised, scaled, or remained fragile in the pilot’s CDE.
Cross-pilot comparison (patterns/configurations)	Standardised pilot narratives + comparable outcome profiles + network evidence + implementation exposure/context evidence.	Which combinations of conditions (ARCHS-informed practices, organisational features, tool integration, network configurations, contextual constraints) are associated with different outcome trajectories.
Toolkit-ready synthesis (inputs to D5.1)	Cross-pilot patterns plus extracted examples, templates and typologies	Transferable guidance on collaborative data practice: what tends to work, for whom, and under which conditions

Table 2. EXCENTRIC change narrative layers

This hybrid methodological framework allows to support a transparent cross-pilot learning process consistent with the project’s logic and implementation. Accordingly, sustainability and competitiveness indicators provide a quantitative backbone for change-over-time assessment, while interpretation is strengthened through triangulation with network evolution and ARCHS-informed qualitative analysis. The pilot narratives and cross-pilot patterns form the basis for the transversal synthesis and for the construction of the Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice (D5.1).

Transversal analysis is framed in EXCENTRIC as a cross-pilot and cross-method comparison aimed at synthesising data from multiple sources into a unified understanding of how conditions and mechanisms - captured through ARCHS, network analysis, accelerator and implementation evidence - relate to sustainability and competitiveness outcomes across pilots.

2.2 Units, levels and waves of analysis

The transversal analysis in EXCENTRIC operates across multiple units and levels of observation, at micro, meso and macro levels. Each pilot – considered both as organisation and as a situated case of CDE development in EXCENTRIC – is analysed over time (T0–T2) to capture how practices, arrangements, and outcomes evolve within specific contexts. (Q)QCA-inspired cross-pilot comparison completes the analysis, allowing transversal learning and enhancing the scalability of fundings.

Table 3 provides an overview of the different waves of analysis in EXCENTRIC and their respective roles.

Wave	Activities	Description
T0 - Baseline and grounding (M1-M12)	Pre-piloting and scoping (executed by Waag and MB), S&C baseline assessment	T0 establishes the baseline conditions and starting profiles of each pilot. It draws on WP2 diagnostics and digital readiness assessment work, early ARCHS-based reflections and assessments. Baseline measurements for sustainability and competitiveness are collected at this stage to enable later comparison of trajectories.
T1 - Implementation monitoring and interim synthesis (M13-M24)	Network mapping and analysis, evolution tracking, Implementation activities, Intermediate transversal synthesis.	T1 corresponds to the active implementation phase (accelerator cycles and tool embedding). Evidence is generated through accelerator monitoring and mentoring traces, structured feedback collected during Demo days (including feedback on ARCHS and on data collection adequacy), and tool-related documentation and feedback. Where feasible, interim network mapping and partial outcome snapshots support an interim transversal synthesis, used for feedback looping to WP3 and WP4 and for the initial cross-cutting theme assessment at M24.
T2 - Consolidation and final synthesis (M25-M36)	Final S&C wave, Final network mapping and analysis, Full transversal cross-case analysis.	T2 captures the endline measurement and cross-pilot synthesis phase. Sustainability and competitiveness outcomes are reassessed (T2) and compared to T0 to derive deltas. Final network mapping and integrated case-file synthesis are completed for each pilot. These materials support the cross-pilot configurational synthesis and directly inform WP6 sustainability strategies, WP7 governance/policy work, and the final Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice (D5.1).

Table 3. Timeline and waves of analysis

The following sections will provide more details on the different methodologies and methodological tools implemented in EXCENTRIC transversal analysis.

2.3 ARCHS as transversal evaluation spine

The orientation of EXCENTRIC’s approach to digital transition is guided by the ARCHS Framework (Derda et al., 2025), which provides a shared reference framework for adaptive, responsible, collaborative, human-centric and sustainable digital transformation. Within this methodological plan, ARCHS operate simultaneously as: (i) a **compass**, offering design and governance guidelines for adaptive, responsible, collaborative, human-centric and sustainable digital transformation; (ii) an **analytical lens**, used for coding and interpreting empirical material across pilots and work packages; (iii) **structuring device for selected measurements**, where items or indicators can be explicitly linked to specific ARCHS dimensions (A/R/C/H/S).

ARCHS is therefore treated as the **connective structure linking principles, practices and outcomes**.

Figure 2. EXCENTRIC ARCHS Model for Smart Digital Transition

In this methodological approach **Sustainability** is treated in two complimentary ways: (i) as an ARCHS principle ('S') that is examined through practices, trade-offs and governance arrangements, and (ii) as an outcome domain assessed through observable trajectories over time within and across pilots.

Competitiveness is treated as an overarching project outcome domain, that is operationalised through pilot-specific indicators and examined in relation to ARCHS-informed practices, tool embedding, and network conditions in the transversal analysis.

ARCHS thus underpins the design and implementation of project activities (WP1–WP4), the transversal analysis (WP5), and the translation of findings into uptake and policy-oriented work (WP6-7). Within WP5, ARCHS provides a shared analytical language for comparing implementation evidence across pilots and for structuring the synthesis that informs the Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice (D5.1).

2.4 Theory of Change and configurational, case-based comparison

EXCENTRIC operates through an iterative cycle of Grounding → Design → Implementation → Assessment. This process logic is translated into a project-level Theory of Change (ToC) that functions as a shared explanation model for how change is expected to happen across all pilots, while recognising that EXCENTRIC does not claim strict counterfactual attribution.⁵ This aligns EXCENTRIC with theory-based evaluation approaches, which use a Theory of Change to structure expectations about how complex interventions work, by specifying mechanisms and contextual conditions rather than only linear cause–effect links.⁶

In EXCENTRIC, the Theory of Change logic does not operate as an experimental causal model, but provides a structured and explicit map of:

- **activities and outputs** (diagnostics, accelerator support, co-creation, tools development and embedding);
- **intermediate change mechanisms** (e.g., adoption of collaborative data practices,

⁵ Bicket, M., Christie, I., Gilbert, N., Penn, A., Hills, D., & Wilkinson, H. (2020). CECAN Evaluation and Policy Practice Note (EPPN) for policy analysts and evaluators - Complexity and what it means for policy design, implementation and evaluation (, Ill.). The Centre for the Evaluation of Complexity Across the Nexus (CECAN). <https://doi.org/10.15126/00853946>

⁶ Blamey, A., & Mackenzie, M. (2007). Theories of change and realistic evaluation. *Evaluation*, 13(4), 439–455. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1356389007082129>

shifts in governance/coordination routines, capability development along ARCHS);

- **outcomes** (organisational sustainability and competitiveness); and
- **conditions** (organisational readiness, network structures, constraints identified in diagnostics, and contextual factors).

Figure 3. Theory of Change in EXCENTRIC

Accordingly, the ToC articulates explicit expectations about how ARCHS-informed collaborative data practices and tools are expected to contribute to sustainability and competitiveness under real-life conditions, using both quantitative and qualitative data. Given the number of pilots and the heterogeneity of their contexts, EXCENTRIC adopts a configurational, case-based comparative logic for cross-pilot analysis. This cross-pilot synthesis is informed by configurational thinking associated with (Q)QCA and is appropriate to conduct comparative analysis when^{7,8}. For each pilot - both as organisation and as an actor within a Collaborative Data Ecosystem - we consider combinations of conditions such as:

- patterns of ARCHS-informed practices and tensions;
- micro/meso/macro network structures and roles;
- the integration, use, and impact of tools and technical solutions and of knowledge transfer and capacity building activities;
- contextual factors identified in diagnostics and implementation.

These configurations are examined in relation to **observed changes in sustainability and competitiveness across levels**. Rather than assuming a single pathway, the transversal analysis allows for the possibility that different combinations of conditions are associated with promising trajectories, or tensions or fragilities in different dimensions (e.g. economic and

⁷ Befani, B. & O'Donnell, M. (2016) Choosing Appropriate Evaluation Methods: A Tool for Assessment and Selection. Bond; Scholz, V, Kirbyshire, A., & Simister N. (2016). Shedding light on causal recipes for development research uptake: Applying Qualitative Comparative Analysis to understand reasons for research uptake. INTRAC and CDKN; Befani, B. & O'Donnell, M. (2016) Choosing Appropriate Evaluation Methods: A Tool for Assessment and Selection. Bond.

⁸ EXCENTRIC logic is compatible with (Quantitative)Qualitative Comparative Analysis ((Q)QCA) and related configurational methods as they (i) treat each case (pilot) as a configuration of conditions and outcomes; (ii) focus on combinations of factors (multiple conjunctural causation) rather than single "drivers"; (iii) accept that different combinations of conditions can lead to similar outcomes, or that similar conditions can lead to different outcomes in different contexts.

cultural sustainability, internal and ecosystem-level competitiveness). To make the relationship between ToC and (Q)QCA explicit: the ToC provides the hypothesised mechanisms and outcome domains (i.e., what should be tracked across pilots), while the (Q)QCA-inspired configurational comparison (including ANT informed SNA) provides the cross-pilot logic for examining which combinations of conditions are associated with different outcome trajectories

2.5 Network Analysis

EXCENTRIC's ambition to develop Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs) within and across pilots requires understanding not only what tools and practices are introduced, but how collaborative data practices become possible in practice: through relationships, alignments, negotiations, and socio-technical arrangements. WP5 therefore treats network analysis as a way to examine the relational and socio-technical conditions under which collaborative data practices are enacted, stabilised, or remain fragile across pilots and over time. Accordingly, the transversal methodology relies on **Actor-Network Theory (ANT)** as the primary interpretive lens with (light) **Social Network Analysis (SNA)** as a complementary descriptive layer. ANT is used to trace how human and non-human actors (e.g., organisational roles, governance arrangements, datasets, tools, platforms, standards, contractual templates) are enrolled into collaborative arrangements and how points of friction, translation, or contestation shape the development of collaborative data practices. SNA is used selectively to support comparability across pilots by providing descriptive network representations (e.g., visual maps and network descriptors) where sufficient data exists, without treating network measures as causal explanations.

Network analysis is organised across three tiers, corresponding to different collaboration arenas relevant to CDE development:

- 1) micro: intra-organisational networks in each pilot,
- 2) meso: inter-organisational collaborations within the Excentric project,
- 3) macro: inter-organisational collaborations across the CCSI landscape.

Across these tiers, the network stream focuses on identifying: (i) **actors and roles** (including who speaks for whom and with what legitimacy), (ii) **obligatory passage points** (e.g., governance decisions, data access requirements, standards, agreements), (iii) **moments of alignment and resistance**, and (iv) **points of tension** that surface ARCHS-relevant trade-offs (e.g., responsibility, human-centricity, collaboration burdens, sustainability constraints) (Figure 4). In this way, network analysis does not function as a stand-alone mapping exercise, but as an interpretive layer that helps explain variation in how collaborative data practices are enacted across pilots.

Actor-Network Theory (ANT) allows for a deep understanding of networks as it conceptualizes every situation as the outcome of dynamic and ongoing associations among diverse actors. In the case of EXCENTRIC, it allows to uncover the negotiation of the challenges and solutions within each pilot. Additionally, it considers both human actors (such as individuals and organizations) and non-human actors (such as data, digital tools, and platforms) as equally influential in shaping networks, explicitly addressing the role of technology within the pilot.

SNA, with a long tradition of uncovering networks of collaboration within the experience sector,⁹ identifies clusters, key actors, and nodes. SNA adds to ANT a more quantitative approach, which visualizes and compares the structure of the networks.

Data sources for the network stream include structured journal notes derived from pilot

⁹ Crossley, N. (2008). Pretty connected.

meetings and project devices (T0 pre-diagnostics/diagnostics sessions, Demo Days/Open Demo Days, accelerator mentoring interactions, and tool implementation moments), complemented where available by project artefacts such as participation lists, workflow maps, onboarding and governance documentation, tool implementation records, and relevant agreements or coordination templates. The initial coding prompts and indicators to operationalise ANT for network interpretation are provided in **Annex C**.

ANT phase	Operational Goal
Problematization	Identifying how the core challenge addressed by the CDE is framed, and how heterogeneous actants (e.g. organisational roles, datasets, platforms, standards, regulators, APIs, users) are defined in relation to that problem.
Interessement	Examining how the CDE attempts to align the interests of diverse actors (e.g. through proposed data-sharing arrangements, standards, incentives, or tool promises), and where alignment is contested or resisted.
Enrollment	Tracing how roles, responsibilities, and routines are negotiated and stabilised, including the adoption of technical infrastructure, governance roles, or data practices.
Mobilisation	Analysing how the network is maintained over time, including how spokespersons, governance arrangements, monitoring tools, or feedback loops act on behalf of the network. Tracing how roles, responsibilities, and routines are negotiated and stabilised, including the adoption of technical infrastructure, governance roles, or data practices.
Translation (overall)	Synthesising the above phases to explain how actors become indispensable to one another, how collaborative data practices are reproduced, and where fragilities or breakdowns persist.

Table 4. ANT-informed Network Analysis Phases

ANT-informed network analysis support integrates the Theory of Change narrative as it (i) contributes to the problem framing and conditions, (ii) provides the mechanism alignment and engagement off CDEs, as well as the (iii) enactment and stabilisation of it. Moreover, its role in the overall transversal methodology is to integrate network properties and configurations which are treated as **conditions and mechanisms/variables for the overall outcome analysis**. Network analysis allows to map which relational configurations, and which positions of human and non-human actors are associated with more robust or more fragile trajectories of change.

Figure 4. ARCHS- and ANT-informed Network Analysis Plan

2.6 Outcome analysis

WP5 assesses sustainability and competitiveness as interpretive change-over-time outcome dimensions at the organisational (pilot) level and at the level of CDE development (i.e., the piloting activities), recognising that (i) pilots operationalise these outcomes through different priorities and constraints, and (ii) some structural effects may extend beyond the project timeframe. Outcome assessment is therefore designed to capture observable trajectories and intermediate outcome signals, and to support a plausible contribution narrative rather than econometric attribution.

Across pilots, through a de-siloed approach, Sustainability is understood as a multidimensional construct – economic, cultural, social and environmental - Competitiveness is interpreted in a context-specific approach, including observable signals. Outcome assessment relies on an Outcome Indicators Bank (Annex B) structured per pilot, derived from Year 1 scoping and diagnostics. The bank divides indicators per pilot, reflecting operational scoping. However, it must be noted that a core/common, transversal indicators are present. Said indicators support the transversal analysis and provide a strong base for the scale up ambition of EXCENTRIC towards the wider CCSI system. Overall EXCENTRIC Theory of Change Outcome measurement follows a **baseline** → **monitoring** → **endline** logic aligned with the overall analysis waves:

- **T0 (baseline):** measurement of starting conditions and initial outcome profiles (drawing on WP2 diagnostics and scoping evidence),
- **T1 (interim signals, where feasible):** partial outcome signals and monitoring evidence, used primarily for learning, sense-making and feedback looping,

- **T2 (endline):** final measurement and consolidation evidence, allowing comparison to T0.

Where quantitative indicators exist, results are processed using a **transparent delta logic**:

- **Normalisation (where appropriate):** indicators may be expressed relative to organisational size or capacity (e.g., per event, per FTE, per comparable season).
- **Aggregation into outcome domains (optional):** indicators may be grouped into outcome domains (e.g., economic sustainability, operational sustainability), without collapsing results into a single index.
- **Change-over-time comparison:** T0 vs. T2 patterns are used to derive outcome trajectories (direction of change and magnitude where observable).

Where baseline information is incomplete, **baseline reconstruction** is documented explicitly (e.g., first-year proxy baselines, retrospective reference points, or structured qualitative baselining). so that limitations and assumptions remain transparent and comparable across pilots.

Outcome analysis is not treated as a standalone numeric exercise. It is strengthened through **triangulation** with:

- ARCHS-coded evidence (practice shifts, tensions, governance decisions),
- tool embedding and usage evidence (WP4),
- accelerator implementation traces and mentoring logs (WP3), and
- network evolution evidence (ANT-informed interpretation, with SNA descriptors where feasible) treated as contextual and enabling conditions.

Coherently with Theory of Change assessment, for each pilot, these inputs are combined into a **pilot change narrative**, describing:

- (i) observed sustainability and competitiveness trajectory (T0 → T2),
- (ii) ARCHS-related capability shifts and tensions,
- (iii) how tool embedding and network conditions enabled or constrained change, and
- (iv) what stabilised, scaled, remained fragile, or did not materialise within the observation window.

The pilot change narrative is the primary within-case synthesis product of WP5 and functions as the core empirical unit for cross-pilot learning. These pilot narratives then serve as the main input for cross-pilot synthesis and for the Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice (D5.1), supported through (Q)QCA-inspired configurational comparison and the cross-pilot matrix of change.

The full set of possible indicators, including core/common domains and pilot-specific measures, is provided in **Annex 2** (Outcome Indicators Bank).

2.7 Cross Pilot (Q)QCA Matrix of Change Logic

To enable structured cross-pilot learning under complexity, WP5 operationalises a QCA-inspired “Matrix of Change” primarily as an interpretive comparative device. Each pilot is treated as a case (N=6) described by a configuration of conditions and an interpreted outcome trajectory. The matrix does not replace within-case interpretation: it builds the pilot change narratives as the primary evidence unit and uses quantitative indicators (where available) as

supportive signals rather than as the main driver of comparison. The Matrix of Change does not function as a stand-alone quantitative model, nor does it replace within-case interpretation. Instead, it is explicitly built on top of the Pilot Change Narratives produced in WP5 (Section 3.6) and provides a transparent structure for cross-case comparison. In this sense, QCA is adopted as a logic of comparison and sensemaking (small-N, multiple pathways, conjunctural causation), not as a mechanical attribution tool. In this matrix, outcomes are expressed as change-over-time deltas (T0→T2; and T1 when feasible) for Sustainability and Competitiveness, while conditions capture key explanatory factors derived from the implementation and transversal evidence base (e.g., organisational readiness, ARCHS-informed practices and tensions, tool embedding intensity, accelerator engagement, and network evolution at micro/meso levels).

Each pilot is therefore represented as a profile combining (i) qualitatively grounded outcome trajectories and (ii) enabling/constraining conditions with quantitative indicators used where available to support interpretation. The matrix functions as the bridge between within-case narratives and cross-case comparison: pilots are compared as configurations of practices, relations, and conditions to identify those associated with more robust (or fragile) sustainability and competitiveness trajectories. This approach is explicitly non-attributional and does not aim to establish counterfactual causality, but rather it supports transparent configurational reasoning under causal complexity, where different combinations of conditions may lead to similar outcomes and similar conditions may produce different trajectories across contexts.

Operationally, the Matrix of Change is built in three linked steps:

1. **Within-case synthesis:** each pilot case file produces a standardised “change narrative” (outcome deltas, ARCHS-coded qualitative data, network descriptors, tool/accelerator embedding traces).
2. **Condition/outcome structuring:** WP5 selects a set of conditions (from the ToC + ARCHS + network analysis) and expresses outcomes as interpretable outcome domains / trajectory statements. Where quantification is feasible, indicators are used to support and triangulate these statements; where quantification is not feasible, structured qualitative baselining and documentary evidence are used, with assumptions made explicit.
3. **Cross-case comparison:** pilots are compared as configurations to identify recurrent patterns (e.g., “high tool embedding + specific ARCHS tensions resolved and strengthened meso-network ties”) associated with stronger S/C trajectories or with stalled/fragile change.

The matrix is updated iteratively: an interim version supports the M24 cross-cutting theme assessment (using T0/T1 evidence and early trajectory signals), and the final version supports endline cross-pilot synthesis (T0/T2 evidence plus consolidation material from WP6-WP7). Findings from the matrix are interpreted alongside the qualitative case narratives and network interpretations (triangulation), to avoid decontextualised readings of small-N patterns and to keep claims proportionate to the evidence. The overall ambition of the cross-pilot transversal analysis is to extract transferable, configuration-based lessons from real-world pilot contexts to inform the Toolkit on Collaborative Data Practice (D5.1) and to support translation into WP6/WP7 outputs (sustainability/upscaling strategies and governance/policy recommendations). Accordingly, the Matrix of Change is treated as a structured bridge from within-case learning to cross-case transferability, not as a statistical proof device.

3. Implementation Plan and Transversal Analysis Weaving

To operationalise the transversal analysis methodology, WP5 follows a structured evidence integration workflow. Across the project, partners generate implementation evidence through diagnostics (WP2), accelerator activities (WP3), and tool development/embedding (WP4). WP5 consolidates this evidence into a consistent analysis structure through:

- **Pilot Case File(s)**
- **Standardised synthesis outputs**, produced at feedback moments; and
- **QCA-inspired Matrix of Change** enabling structured cross-pilot comparison

At key moments (Demo Days, Open Demo Days, sprint retrospectives, and LABs), evidence capture is standardised and shared to allow cross work package and knowledge transfer. The project implementation evidence and the network and transversal analysis evidence operate in a looping structure. In line with WP5 objectives and Task T1.2, WP5 produces interim synthesis outputs which are used to (i) refine accelerator support and mentoring (WP3), (ii) support iterative tool development and documentation (WP4), and (iii) feed forward into sustainability planning and governance recommendations (WP6–WP7). Operational details of data stream integration and feedback looping are provided in **Annex D**.

4. Conclusions

This document establishes the transversal analysis methodology and plan for WP5 in EXCENTRIC. It clarifies how WP5 functions as the project's transversal sensemaking and integration layer, linking implementation evidence to a coherent analysis of how Collaborative Data Ecosystems (CDEs) are enacted and stabilised in real-life CCSI settings, and how these processes are plausibly envisioned to relate to trajectories of sustainability and competitiveness across six pilots. WP5 adopts a hybrid methodological approach combining (i) Theory of Change (ToC) to structure expected pathways from activities and outputs to intermediate mechanisms and outcomes; (ii) Network analysis combining Social Network Analysis (SNA) with Actor-Network Theory (ANT) to describe evolving actor configurations (human and non-human) and points of tension in the formation of Collaborative Data Practices; and (iii) a (Q)QCA-inspired cross-pilot configurational logic operationalised through a Matrix of Change to enable structured cross-case learning under complexity. A key characteristic of the approach is that sustainability and competitiveness outcomes are treated as observable trajectories, interpreted through a combination of indicators and triangulated qualitative insights. Outcome assessment follows a baseline-monitoring-endline logic aligned with the project waves (T0–T2), while explicitly recognising that (i) pilots operationalise sustainability and competitiveness differently due to context and constraints, and (ii) some structural outcomes may extend beyond the project observation window. Accordingly, WP5 prioritises outcome profiles and narrative plausibility: quantitative indicators provide a transparent backbone for change-over-time assessment, while interpretation is strengthened – and informed – through qualitative data, compassed by ARCHS and network evolution descriptors, treasuring real-life operational settings from piloting activities, such as tool embedding evidence and accelerator traces.

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6. Appendices

ANNEX A – ARCHS Measurement and Inquiry Framework

1A. ARCHS Individual-Level Survey

The survey focuses on **individual perspective** of CCSI workforce: how they personally experience adaptability, responsibility, collaboration, human-centricity and sustainability (ARCHS) in daily work.

Principle 1: Adaptability

This section looks at how flexible and resilient you can be at work, and how your workplace supports this. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Flexibility

1. The leadership of my organisation provides me with continuous learning opportunities.
2. My immediate boss provides me with useful feedback on my work.
3. The leadership of my company promotes and supports my digital transformation journey.
4. The use of digital tools allows me more flexibility in organising my work hours.
5. The leadership of my organisation provides me with good management practices for adapting to changes.

Resilience

6. I know my personal strengths and I use them regularly in my work.
7. The work that I do fits well with my personal values and beliefs.
8. I have a strong and reliable network of supportive colleagues at work.
9. My workplace is somewhere where I feel that I belong.
10. I have developed some reliable ways to deal with the personal stress of challenging events at work

Principle 2: Responsibility

This section is about how you personally handle data and follow legal and ethical guidelines at your workplace. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

Personal understanding of data management:

11. I am aware data processing must comply with existing legislation, including the GDPR.
12. When processing personal data, I ask for the consent of the persons whose data I want to process.
13. I inform data subjects about the purposes and conditions for which personal data will be used.
14. I inform data subjects about their rights on their data, including the right to withdraw consent to the processing of their data.

15. I inform data subjects at the moment of collection or at a later moment when their data will be transferred to third parties.

Following Legal Guidelines:

16. When processing personal data, I rely on other legal basis different than consent.

17. I follow specific guidelines regarding the processing (collection, use, sharing) of non-personal data.

18. When in doubt about the lawfulness of data processing, I seek specialist legal advice.

19. I follow specific guidelines or codes of conduct regarding the processing (collection, use, sharing) of data.

20. I follow specific guidelines or codes of conduct regarding the processing (collection, use, sharing) of personal data.

Principle 3: Collaboration

This section is about how you work with others, share responsibility, and build trust.

Please think about your experience in previous collaborative projects within this organisation (for example, major cross-departmental work or joint initiatives with external partners).

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

21. I had a clear understanding of what our collaboration was trying to accomplish.

22. I had a clear understanding of my role, rights and responsibilities.

23. I trusted my colleagues.

24. I was informed as often as I should be about what is going on in the collaboration.

25. I felt my contributions were valued and I was able to raise concerns openly.

Principle 4: Human-Centricity

This section focuses on how digital tools affect your skills, wellbeing, and satisfaction at work. To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

26. My competences and skills are sufficient to be proficient in new IT tools implemented at my workplace.

27. Over the past 12 months, I have been offered opportunities for getting training on a digital tool (paid by employer, on the job training, etc).

28. I receive support with technical issues after having completed the training.

29. I feel irritated in connection with new ICT solutions which have affected my professional duties/tasks.

30. I am able to customise digital tools to optimise my workflow.

Principle 5: Sustainability

This section is about your views on economic, cultural and environmental sustainability.

To what extent do you agree with the following statements?

31. Organizational practices can positively influence employees to act more sustainably.
32. Digitalization and sustainability can reinforce each other rather than conflict.
33. Reducing people’s carbon footprint is essential for a sustainable future.
34. Respecting and valuing cultural differences is essential for a sustainable future.
35. Cultural sustainability depends on preserving traditions first, before adapting to new demands.

1B. ARCHS-Oriented Lines of Inquiry (Qualitative Framework)¹⁰

ARCHS dimension	Sub-dimension	Line of inquiry
Adaptive	Flexibility	Flexible Leadership
		Flexible workplace
		Innovation Flexibility
	Resilience	External resources
		Minimization of silos
		Proactive posture
		Internal resilience
Collaborative	Collaboration Readiness	Collaboration history
		External context
		Internal context
		Network setup
	Collective Ownership of Goals	
	Communication & Knowledge Sharing	
	Flexibility	
	Formalization & Governance	
	Resource Availability & Allocation	
Trust		
Human-Centric	Collaboration and Innovation	Empowerment
	Digital Literacy	Existing skills
		Training Opportunities
	Employee Satisfaction	Empowerment
Human – Organization Relationship	Goal alignment	

¹⁰ Responsibility and Sustainability will serve as separate lines of inquiry that will be developed after the finalization of pilots scoping process.

1C. Collaboration success survey¹¹

- (i) How successful is this collaboration at implementing strategies to address collaboration goals and objectives?
- (ii) How successful is this collaboration at achieving its current goals and objectives?
- (iii) How successful is this collaboration in making a difference within the community it serves?
- (iv) How confident are you that this collaboration network will still exist in the community two years from now?
- (v) How confident are you that this collaboration will continue to successfully achieve its goals and objectives?
- (vi) How confident are you that this collaboration will continue to make a difference within the community it serves?
- (vii) In comparison to the efforts of a single partnering agency/organization, how effective is this collaboration in achieving its goals and objectives?
- (viii) In comparison to the efforts of a single partnering agency/organization, how efficient is this collaboration in achieving its goals and objectives?

ANNEX 2 – Outcome Indicators Bank

The table below provides an Outcome Indicators Bank for Sustainability and Competitiveness. It functions as a tracking and measurement reference: a structured set of possible indicators that can be selected, operationalised, and reported consistently across pilots in line with their operational scoping and feasible data sources. The Indicator Bank is grounded in Year 1 scoping and diagnostics, and is therefore provisional and adaptive: indicators may be refined, replaced, or complemented as piloting and data availability evolve. Importantly, the Indicators Bank does not constitute “outcomes” in itself; rather, it supports the systematic monitoring and documentation of measurable signals that can later inform pilot-level synthesis and change interpretation.

Indicator name	Description	Formula / operationalisation
S1. Returning visitor rate	Share of attendees who return within a defined period/season.	Returning unique attendees / Total unique attendees
S2. Season-to-season retention	% of last season’s audience returning within same programming/edition.	Unique attendees in season t who also attended season t-1 / Unique attendees season t-1.
S3. Subscription renewal rate	Renewal of subscriptions/season tickets.	Renewed subscriptions / Subscriptions eligible for renewal.
S4. Membership renewal rate	Renewal of membership programmes.	Renewed members / Members eligible for renewal.
S5. Donor retention rate	Repeat donation behaviour across periods.	Repeat donors / Donors in previous period.

¹¹ Marek, L. I., Brock, D.-J. P., & Savla, J. (2014). Evaluating collaboration for effectiveness: Conceptualization and measurement.

S6. Audience satisfaction score	Overall satisfaction (post-event survey).	Mean (satisfaction item)
S7. Perceived value score	Perceived value for time/money/experience.	Mean (value items); optionally standardised: $(x - \min)/(\max - \min)$.
S8. Programme–audience fit (Relevance index)	Index: resonance/fit, inclusivity, perceived meaning/learning, quality.	Mean (standardised relevance items);
S9. Audience attachment / belonging index	Emotional/identity connection and intention to stay connected.	Mean (attachment items) (scale index).
S10. Recommendation intention (NPS / WTR)	Likelihood to recommend (single item or NPS).	If NPS: %Promoters (9–10) – %Detractors (0–6); else Mean
S11. Complaint rate	Service friction proxy: complaints relative to attendance.	#Complaints / #Attendances (or per 1,000 attendances).
S12. No-show rate	Attendance reliability where tickets/reservations exist.	#No-shows / #Tickets issued (or #No-shows / #Reservations).
S13. Capacity utilisation rate	Average attendance relative to capacity (per event).	For each event: Attendance/Capacity; then Mean
S14. Utilisation volatility	Stability of utilisation across events (planning stability).	SD(utilisation per event) or CV = SD/Mean.
S15. Forecast accuracy (attendance)	Accuracy of operational forecasts vs actuals.	Mean Absolute Percentage Error
S16. Coordination burden (hours)	Staff hours spent on coordination per period/event.	Sum(coordination hours); normalised: / #events or / FTE.
S17. Process cycle time (coordination)	Time to complete key coordination process.	Median(end_time – start_time) per process instance.
S18. Manual work share	Manual vs tool-supported work in a defined process.	Manual task-hours / Total task-hours (or Manual tasks / Total tasks).
S19. Data completeness rate	Completeness of required fields for reporting.	#Completed required fields / #Total required fields
S20. Data quality score	Accuracy/consistency/timeliness rubric.	Rubric: Mean(score_accuracy, score_consistency, score_timeliness) (0–n).
S21. Tool adoption rate (active users)	Share of targeted users who used tool in last X weeks.	#Active users / #Targeted users (define “active”: ≥1 meaningful action).
S22. Routine embedding score	Degree tool is embedded into routine decisions (meetings/planning).	Rubric or count: #Routine uses per month; or Mean(embedding scale items).
S23. Tool reuse rate	Reuse across productions/use cases (Dortmund-type pilots).	#Productions/use cases using tool / #Eligible productions/use cases.
S24. Tool reliability (incident rate)	Failures/incidents per usage.	#Incidents / #Sessions (or per production).

S25. Training coverage	Coverage of training for staff in scope.	#Trained staff / #Staff in scope.
S26. Data capability confidence	Self-reported capability/confidence to work with data/tools.	Mean(capability/confidence items) (scale index).
S27. Partnership continuity rate	Retention of strategic partners.	#Continuing strategic partners / #Strategic partners previous period.
S28. Funding renewal outcome	Renewal success for key funding streams.	#Renewed funding agreements / #Agreements up for renewal (plus binary per funder).
S29. Revenue volatility	Stability of core revenues across comparable periods.	CV(revenue) = SD(revenue)/Mean(revenue) (lower is better).
S30. Revenue diversification index	Dependence on a single revenue stream vs diversified mix.	1 - HHI, where HHI = $\sum(\text{share}_i^2)$ across revenue sources.
S31. Audience diversity index	Diversity of audience composition (dimensions defined per pilot).	Shannon: $H = -\sum(p_i \ln p_i)$; or share in underrepresented groups.
S32. Programming diversity index	Portfolio diversity (genres/voices/regions).	Shannon/Simpson as above; or rubric if qualitative.
S33. Inclusion perception score	Perceived inclusivity/accessibility of offer.	Mean (inclusion items) (scale index).
S34. Proximal legacy readiness score	Signals that legacy is likely (governance, documentation, ownership).	Rubric: sum of binary items (0/1) or Mean (rubric items) \rightarrow 0-n.
C1. New audience acquisition rate	Share of first-time attendees (or target segments) this period.	#First-time attendees / #Total unique attendees (or segment-specific).
C2. Audience growth rate	Growth in total attendances or unique attendees.	(Attendances _t - Attendances _{t-1}) / Attendances _{t-1} .
C3. Digital reach growth	Growth in relevant online reach/participation.	(Online reach _t - Online reach _{t-1}) / Online reach _{t-1} .
C4. Offsite/hybrid reach ratio	Extent of reach beyond physical attendance.	Offsite/hybrid participants / Total participants (onsite+offsite).
C5. Non-local reach share	Share of audience beyond local catchment.	#Non-local participants / #Total participants.
C6. Partner acquisition rate	New strategic partners gained.	#New strategic partners / period (or % increase).
C7. Strategic partner quality score	Weighted importance of partners (define weights).	$\sum(\text{weight_partner}_j)$ where weights are predefined (e.g., 1-3).
C8. Network centrality (degree)	Network position from SNA (connectivity).	Degree centrality per node; pilot summary: Mean degree or pilot ego-network degree.
C9. Network brokerage (betweenness)	Brokerage/bridging role in ecosystem.	Betweenness centrality; pilot summary: Mean/median betweenness of key actors.

C10. Collaboration breadth (sector diversity)	Diversity of partner types/sectors.	Shannon: $H = -\sum(p_i \ln p_i)$ across partner sectors.
C11. Competitive funding success rate	Success rate in competitive calls.	#Successful applications / #Submitted applications.
C12. New funding sources secured	New funders/sponsors added.	Count(new funding sources) (qualified definition).
C13. Visibility/recognition index	Media mentions, awards, invitations (weighted).	Σ (weighted visibility events) (weights defined; e.g., award=3, mention=1).
C14. Comparative positioning signals	Invitations to networks, co-productions, tours, showcases.	Count(positioning signals) (coded list; optionally weighted).
C15. Innovation adoption rate (new format/tool)	Uptake of new offerings introduced via pilot.	Users of new format / Total users (or adoption over time).
C16. Replication/transfer interest	External interest to adopt/replicate.	Count(qualified external inquiries) (qualification rule defined).
C17. Stakeholder legitimacy score	Perceived credibility/trust from funders/partners.	Mean(legitimacy items) (survey/interview coded to scale).
C18. Accountability evidence strength (SROI pack score)	Quality/completeness of evidence used in funder dialogue.	Rubric: Mean(rubric items) or Sum(binary components present).
C19. Negotiation friction proxy	Effort/friction in funder renewal conversations.	Quant: #Iterations to agreement or Time-to-agreement; Qual: Mean(friction scale).
C20. Resource mobilisation capacity	Ability to mobilise resources/partners quickly.	Count(mobilised contributions); optionally normalised / period.
C21. Differentiation perception score	Perceived distinctiveness vs peers (audience/stakeholders).	Mean(differentiation items) (scale).
C22. Submission volume (talent attraction)	For open calls: volume of applications/submissions.	Count(submissions); optionally normalised / call duration.
C23. Outreach conversion rate	Effectiveness of outreach to participation.	#Participants attributable to outreach / #Contacts reached.
C24. Ecosystem uptake signals	Evidence that others reference/use outputs (toolkit/tools).	Count(verified uptake cases) (verification rule defined).

ANNEX 3 – Actor Network Theory – Exploration Lines

Stage	Code (Node)	Description / Guidance
Problematisation	Observed Problem(s)	What core challenges or gaps are actors identifying (e.g., digital skill deficit, funding, collaboration)?
	Who defines the problem?	Identify the actors (individuals or institutions) articulating the issue.
	To whom is the problem addressed?	Who is being positioned as affected or responsible?
	Proposed Obligatory Passage Point (OPP)	What solution is being proposed as necessary or inevitable?
	Who positions themselves as indispensable?	Which actor or tool claims to be the key enabler of the solution?
	Excluded Actors or Perspectives	Whose perspectives or tools are not being acknowledged or are being bypassed?
	Discursive Framing / Narrative	How is the problem framed (e.g., 'urgent need for upskilling')?
	Material Elements Involved	What non-human actors are used to define or illustrate the problem?
	Conflicts or Tensions Noted	Are there disagreements over what the real problem is or how it should be addressed?
	Emergent Roles Suggested by the Problem	What roles are implicitly or explicitly created by the way the problem is defined?
Interessement	Key Actors Being Interested	Who is being targeted or recruited into the network?
	Mechanisms of Interessement	What strategies/tools are used to convince or attract actors?
	Resistance or Refusal	Are there actors rejecting or resisting their proposed roles?
	Gatekeepers or Mediators	Are there intermediaries helping (or hindering) the interessement process?
	Tools or Materials Used to Align Interest	Are physical or digital objects playing a role?
	How Roles Are Defined or Framed	How is each actor's role described?
	Signs of Acceptance or Hesitation	Verbal/non-verbal cues indicating willingness or reluctance.
	Competing Interessement Attempts	Are there conflicting efforts to enroll actors into different networks?
	Temporal Elements	Is timing or urgency used to enforce interessement?
Enrollment	Roles Being Taken or Negotiated	What roles are actors adopting, contesting, or negotiating?

	Scripts or Programs of Action	What are the expected behaviors or routines assigned to each role?
	Delegation	Are tasks or decisions being delegated? To whom?
	Stabilizing or Destabilizing Factors	What factors are strengthening or weakening enrollment?
	Alignment Between Actors	Are goals and expectations becoming aligned across actors?
	Formalization	Is enrollment being codified (e.g., via roles, documentation)?
	Narratives of Participation	How do actors describe their involvement?
	Non-Human Actors' Role	What tools or documents enforce or support enrollment?
	Tensions or Role Drift	Are there signs of roles shifting or diverging?
Mobilisation	Identified Spokesperson(s)	Who represents others in meetings, reports, etc.?
	Whose Interests Are Represented?	Whose voices or concerns are being spoken for?
	Legitimacy and Recognition	How is the spokesperson legitimized?
	Methods of Speaking for Others	How do spokespersons act on behalf of others?
	Stability of Representation	Are there disputes over representation?
	Mobilization of Non-Human Actors	Are tools or systems acting as proxies or representatives?
	Scaling Up	How does representation move to the institutional or sector level?
	Feedback Loops	Do represented actors have the ability to contest or reshape their representation?
	Visibility vs. Invisibility	Are certain actors made more visible or invisible?

ANNEX 4 – Feedback Loop Data Structure and Data Stream Master Tables

EXCENTRIC operates through an iterative cycle of Grounding → Design → Implementation → Assessment, which aligns with Theory of Change based methodologies. The project implementation evidence and the transversal analysis evidence operate in a looping structure.¹² Such looping allows for sensemaking venues, where (i) pilots and stakeholders validate emerging interpretations, (ii) feedback is collected on ARCHS and on the feasibility/burden of data collection, and (iii) new relations and collaboration opportunities become visible for network analysis. Accordingly, the transversal analysis (i) refines accelerator support and mentoring (WP3), (ii) supports iterative tool development and documentation (WP4), and (iii) drives forward into sustainability planning and governance

¹² The loop structure allows to avoid the pitfall of one-off, ex-post evaluation, as interim findings are intended to feed back into (i) the design and focus of accelerator content and mentoring (WP3); (ii) the refinement and documentation of tools and technical solutions (WP4); (iii) the development of sustainability strategies and templates (WP6); (iv) the formulation of metrics and governance recommendations (WP7).

recommendations (WP6–WP7).

Timing (month/phase)	Feedback moment (project device)	What gets captured (data)	Inputs from
M12/13 (pilots files and card)	Pilots Cards	Crystalized feedback and roadmap on piloting activities resulting from scoping	WP3 Accelerator Mentoring focus; WP4 Tool Development
M13 (kick-off DD)	Demo Day Kick Off	Structured feedback on pilot challenge framing + early collaboration signals	WP3 Accelerator mentoring focus; WP4 Tool Development
WP3/WP4 (sprints)	Sprint reviews / retrospectives / check-ins	Mentor notes, barriers/enablers, feasibility/burden of data collection	WP3 adjustments; WP4 iteration
M16/17, M20/21, M24/25	Open Demo Days	Feedback from broader sector; new connections; adoption/translation signals	WP5 network analysis; WP8 dissemination; WP7 relevance
M24	Initial network analysis + cross-cutting theme assessment	Network barriers/challenges + pilot relevance to transversal themes	WP3/WP4 recalibration; inputs for WP6/WP7
M25–36	Sustainability planning moments	What “stuck”, what is scalable, governance constraints	WP6 strategies; WP7 governance recs
M36	EXCENTRIC LABs	Skills/Policy/Market uptake outputs + stakeholder validation	WP5 toolkit; WP7 policy package

Cross-WP streams of the measurement architecture are provided in the following Tables. This section provides an overview of the main data streams produced, collected, and analyzed in the EXCENTRIC project and feeding the network and transversal analysis. Table 4.1A lists implementation-generated evidence (WP1-WP4, WP6-WP8) that will be systematically reused in WP5, Table 4.1B lists how WP5 enables cross work packages data

Real-life implementation projects such as EXCENTRIC generate numerous streams of data through different WPs and phases. Tables below provide an overview of the main data streams produced, collected, and analyzed in the EXCENTRIC project and feeding the network and transversal analysis. Table 4.1A lists implementation-generated evidence (WP1-WP4, WP6-WP8) that will be systematically reused in WP5, Table 4.1B lists how WP5 enables cross work packages data synthesis.

Table 4.1A - Implementation generated data streams

WP (origin)	Evidence stream / instrument	Data type	Primary analytical role for WP5	Feedback-to / use
WP1	ARCHS framework materials (definitions, sub-dimensions,	Framework structured +	Common analytical spine	WP2-WP5; supports

	question banks; reflection & assessment questions)	qual/quant items	(coding frame + measurement structure) enabling comparability across pilots	refinement of ARCHS through evidence/partner feedback
WP2	T0 diagnostic baseline (pilot context, org profile, “starting point” for DT and CDE)	Mixed (profiles, notes, baseline descriptors)	Baseline context + starting conditions for cross-pilot comparison	Inputs to WP3 tailoring + WP5 baseline reconstruction
WP2	Digital-Maturity Diagnostic Kit (D2.1) (as part of WP2 design outputs)	Structured diagnostic outputs (e.g., scores/ratings + structured notes)	Baseline condition + calibration of “organisational readiness” for interpreting later change	WP3 design; WP5 baseline conditions
WP2	Digital Readiness assessment outputs (DR)	Mixed (assessment results + constraints/opportunities narrative)	Mechanism-context evidence: constraints/opportunities shaping feasible pathways	WP3 tailoring; WP4 scoping; WP5 interpretation
WP2	Value Sensitive Design (VSD) outputs (workshops/artifacts informing design choices)	Qualitative workshop material + design artifacts	Captures value trade-offs + “why this design” logic; supports later explanation of adoption/resistance	WP3/WP4 iteration; WP5 interpretation
WP2	Pilot challenge framing + operational flows gathered during design (as used to inform accelerator & tools)	Mixed (notes, process maps, requirements)	Defines initial “problem framing” per pilot (what is being tested)	WP3/WP4; WP5 case narratives
WP3	Accelerator implementation: three six-month “sprints” (co-creation of use cases)	Process documentation + sprint outputs	Core implementation evidence: what was actually done, when, with whom	WP5 mechanism tracing; supports mid-course learning
WP3	Accelerator monitoring (check-ins, mentoring/coaching notes, sprint reflections/retrospectives)	Process logs / qualitative	Mechanism/process evidence (how change happens; barriers/enablers)	WP3 adjustments; WP4 iteration; WP5 explanation
WP3	Demo days / open days: participation + structured feedback (incl. feedback on ARCHS framing + “what data is missing / not captured”)	Event feedback + traces	Validation + sensemaking moments; signals on network activation and framework fit	WP3/WP4 iteration; WP5 triangulation
WP4	User feedback on tools (structured feedback, testing notes; where feasible,	Mixed (qual feedback + usage traces)	Adoption/fit evidence: explains variation in	WP4 iteration; WP5 explanation

	aggregated usage analytics)		outcomes and network effects	(GDPR-compatible aggregation where relevant)
WP6	Pilots closure & sustainability planning outputs (T6.1) + Pilots report & sustainability strategy (D6.1)	Reports + case studies + reusable templates/scenarios	Consolidation evidence: what “stuck”, what is scalable, and what enabling conditions / governance constraints emerged; validates pilot change narratives and strengthens cross-pilot synthesis	Feeds WP5 final synthesis (toolkit extraction); informs WP7 translation into policy package; provides content for WP8 dissemination
WP6	Uptake programme: EXCENTRIC LABs (Skills Lab / Policy Lab / Accelerator-to-Market Lab) (T6.2) + Uptake program – Final Report (D6.2)	Event outputs + participation records + stakeholder feedback (qual/structured)	External sensemaking + uptake evidence: captures translation/uptake conditions, stakeholder reactions, and ecosystem-level validation of emerging lessons; supports triangulation of network/outcome interpretations	Feeds WP5 toolkit-ready lessons; supports WP7 policy labs / recommendations; supports WP8 outreach and exploitation framing
WP7	CDP metrics work (T7.1) + Smart Guide & policy recommendations development (T7.2) + Policy package (D7.1)	Metrics set + policy outputs + workshop outputs (mixed)	Translation + feasibility check layer: converts transversal findings into metrics and governance recommendations; helps validate whether cross-pilot lessons are actionable for policy and multipliers	Feeds WP5 packaging of final synthesis; informs WP8 dissemination targeting; strengthens external uptake / governance framing
WP8	Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation deliverables (D8.1 / D8.2 / D8.3) + communication materials & engagement traces (website/social/newsletters/pres s/podcast) + stakeholder engagement & network	Communication traces + engagement analytics + participation lists + dissemination artefacts	Reach/uptake context evidence: documents who was engaged, when, and through which devices; supports interpretation of network activation	Supports WP5 interpretation (network growth/activation context); supports WP6 LAB participation

	outreach tasks (T8.1–T8.4)		signals around demo/open days, LABs, tour events and stakeholder outreach	and uptake evidence; supports WP7 stakeholder mobilisation and policy uptake pathways
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Table 4.1B - Transversal Analysis data streams and overall integration

WP5 element	Instrument / artefact	What it integrates (inputs)	What it produces (output)	Feedback-to / use
WP5	Network survey + mapping protocol (micro/meso/macro)	WP2 orbit mapping + WP3 event participation + WP4 tool-related actors (where relevant)	Sociograms + network metrics + comparable network descriptors across pilots	Feeds WP3 (community/mentorship focus), WP6 (sustainability), WP7 (governance)
WP5	ARCHS-in-practice evidence capture (ARCHS lens applied to qualitative material and implementation traces)	WP1 ARCHS spine + WP2–WP4 logs/artefacts + pilot feedback moments	Comparable ARCHS-coded evidence across pilots (tensions, practices, enablers/barriers)	Supports ARCHS refinement; informs toolkit typologies
WP5	Sustainability & Competitiveness outcome instrument (baseline + delta logic)	Baseline context (WP2) + implementation exposure (WP3/WP4) + qualitative evidence	Dimension scores + deltas per pilot; outcome profiles	Feeds WP6 sustainability strategies/templates + WP7 metrics/policy
WP5	Pilot Case File template (“one folder per pilot”)	All Table 4.1A streams	Standardised within-case narrative enabling cross-case comparison	Backbone for WP5 synthesis; re-usable for WP6/WP7
WP5	Cross-pilot synthesis matrix (conditions × outcomes)	Case files + outcome deltas + network descriptors	Configurational comparison dataset (QQCA-inspired logic)	Feeds D5.1 toolkit structure + WP7 governance framing
WP5	M24 interim synthesis note (“initial network analysis and cross-cutting theme assessment”)	T0/T1 network evidence + implementation traces + early outcome signals (if available)	Interim findings on network barriers/enablers + cross-cutting themes	Feeds WP3 accelerator adjustments + WP4 tool refinement

WP5	Final transversal synthesis (towards D5.1)	Full integrated evidence base	Final cross-pilot findings packaged for toolkit + policy	Feeds WP6 upscaling + WP7 policy recommendations
WP5	Sustainability planning extraction grid (from WP6 outputs) + “what stuck / scalable” coding sheet	D6.1 pilots report & sustainability strategy + WP6 case studies/templates/scenarios + WP6 closure reflections	Validated “sustainability & upscaling” evidence layer per pilot + cross-pilot lessons on enabling conditions/constraints	Feeds D5.1 toolkit (templates/typologies); informs WP7 policy feasibility; supports WP6 upscaling narrative
WP5	Policy translation interface (metrics ↔ findings)	WP5 cross-pilot synthesis + WP6 uptake evidence + WP7 metrics/recommendations workflow (T7.1–T7.2 / D7.1)	Traceable mapping from transversal findings → candidate metrics → policy recommendations / Smart Guide inputs	Feeds WP7 Policy Package (D7.1); aligns toolkit claims with policy-facing framing; supports stakeholder validation moments
WP5	Dissemination & stakeholder engagement context log (uptake traces)	WP8 communication/dissemination outputs (D8.1–D8.3) + outreach participation lists + event traces (tour, open demo days, etc.)	Context layer for interpreting network activation + uptake signals (who engaged, when, and around what artefacts)	Informs WP5 interpretation of network growth/activation; supports WP6 LAB recruitment/participation evidence; supports WP7 mobilisation strategy